

Anxiety And Depression In Teachers In The Context Of The Return To Face-To-Face Education

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Abstract

The objective was to determine the degree of correlation between anxiety and depression in teachers of the educational institutions of the Local Educational Management Unit 01, Lima - Peru, 2022. It is important to indicate that this study confirms the widespread prevalence of depression in the teaching community, which is related to how other studies have shown that it affects students' academic performance. The method used was the hypothetical deductive, descriptive and cross-sectional correctional design. The population consisted of 60 regular elementary school teachers. Data were obtained through a survey, and two questionnaires based on the Likert scale were used as instruments. In addition, the same data were processed through the Spearman rho statistical analysis. The results indicate that there is a 0.854 correlation between both variables. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a positive or direct relationship between teachers' anxiety and depression.

Keywords: depression, anxiety, teachers, elementary education

Resumen

El objetivo fue determinar el grado de correlación entre la ansiedad y la depresión en los docentes de las instituciones educativas de la Unidad de Gestión Educativa Local 01, Lima – Perú, 2022. Es importante indicar que este estudio confirma la prevalencia generalizada de la depresión en la comunidad docente, lo que tiene que ver cómo otros estudios han demostrado, que afecta el rendimiento académico de los estudiantes. El método empleado fue el hipotético deductivo, de tipo descriptivo y de diseño correccional transversal. La población estuvo integrada por 60 docentes de educación básica regular. La obtención de datos se realizó mediante la encuesta y como instrumento se emplearon dos cuestionarios establecidos en la escala de Likert. Los mismos datos fueron procesados a través del análisis estadístico rho Spearman. Los resultados indican que existe el 0.854 de correlación entre ambas variables. Se concluye que existe relación positiva o directa entre la ansiedad y la depresión de los docentes.

Palabras clave: depresión, ansiedad, docentes, educación básica

1. Introduction

Anxiety is a normal human emotion, as are joy, surprise and fear (Andrades-Tobar et al., 2021; Cabezas-Heredia et al., 2021; Sigüenza and Vílchez, 2021). Common reasons for anxiety include social pressure, work, study or stress related to meeting deadlines (Chacón Delgado et al., 2021; García Muñoz and Trujillo Camacho, 2022; Suclupe-Navarro et al., 2021). Anxiety disorders are the most prevalent worldwide (Alvites-Huamaní, 2019; Ramos-Galarza, 2017; Vega-Dienstmaier, 2019). On the one hand, Sanchez et al. (2022) state that anxiety disorders constitute the most prevalent group, followed by mood disorders.

On the one hand, Alvites-Huamaní (2019) states that people with generalized anxiety disorders have recurrent fears or worries, such as health or financial situation, and often constantly feel that something bad is about to happen. On the other hand, the cause of these intense feelings of anxiety can be difficult to identify (Martínez-García et al., 2022; Morales Beltrán et al., 2022; Vizioli & Pagan, 2021).

On the other hand, depression is a mental disorder characterized fundamentally by low mood and feelings of sadness, associated with alterations in behavior, activity level and thinking (Armas-Elguera et al., 2021; Gutierrez et al., 2021; Malonda, 2018). In the same vein, Vega-Dienstmaier (2019) asserts that the beginning of depression is an emotional disorder that causes a feeling of constant sadness and a loss of interest in performing different activities. Furthermore, the increase of the most common mental disorders, such as depression and anxiety, in young adults and college students is becoming a worldwide concern (Gómez-Coca et al., 2022; University of Murcia. et al., 2009; Vizioli & Pagano, 2020).

During the covid-19 context, several researchers concluded that teachers, many of them on their initiative, were developing their classes virtually with their students so that they would not lose the school year (Ocaña and Gavilanes, 2022; Rodríguez-Martínez et al., 2018; Said-Hung et al., 2021), since it was inevitable to lose the school year.

In that scenario, the limitations of technology were seen, the uncertainty of knowing if their students were attending and learning, so it was quite difficult for both students and

teachers themselves, as the best way of teaching students is seen the similarity in some cases and the difference is found in the use of computer tools and platforms, must have been used in institutions and educational workers (Davila and Espinoza, 2020; Grande et al., 2002; Priestnall et al., 2020; Roseth et al., 2021).

All this generated anxiety in the teachers since they were afraid that the internet connectivity would be lost, they would struggle to capture the attention of the students, and that the classes would not be interrupted by an external agent such as animals, a relative, these conditions were not optimal, there was no good environment at home to develop the classes, in addition to the lack of training in information technologies such as virtual meetings zoom, Google meets, made the teachers and even more the children of the first and initial grades, go through real anxiety.

UGEL 01, located in Lima in the San Juan de Miraflores district, was no stranger to the above reality. Many teachers, parents and students voluntarily commented that the technologies were not within their reach (Grande et al., 2002; Moreno Hernandez, 2021; OSIPTEL et al., 2021), which did not allow for educational development.

Because of this situation, the objective of this research was to determine the degree of relationship between anxiety and depression in teachers of the educational institutions of the Local Educational Management Unit 01, Lima - Peru, 2022.

2. Method And Materials

Type and design

This research corresponds to the hypothetical deductive method of descriptive type and cross-sectional correctional design; since the work proceeded from the observation of the phenomenon to be studied, the theoretical bases allowed the formulation of the hypothesis and the implications of the results were deduced (Graw-hill et al., 2006; Herber, 2012; Lopez and Sandoval, 2015).

Variables

Table 1. *Variables and their dimensions*

Variables	Dimensions
Anxiety (Zung, 2006)	- Cognitive,
	- Physiological
	- Motor
Depression (Beck, 1994)	- Anhedonic humor
	- Anergy
	- Discommunication

Population

The study worked with the entire population, that is, 120 teachers of Regular Basic Education of the Unidad de Gestión Educativa Local 01, in the district of San Juan de Miraflores (Lima - Peru).

Instruments

The “Zung Anxiety Test” (Zung, 2006) was applied to measure anxiety indexes. This instrument is characterized by a closed, dimensional structure and established on the Likert scale (1=never and 5 always). A pilot test determined a 0.75 Cronbach’s alpha reliability.

To measure the indices of DEPRESSION, the author's "Beck Test" (Beck, 1994) was applied. This instrument is characterized by a closed, dimensional structure and established on the Likert Scale (1=never and 5 always). A pilot test determined a 0.75 Cronbach's alpha reliability.

Statistical processing

The data were analyzed using Spearman's rho test since the data were parametric (Ortega et al., 2009).

Ethical considerations

Data collection was done with the prior consent of the participants. There were no conflicts of interest in any aspect.

3. Results

Frequency table Depression

Gender Of Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	WOMAN	44	72.1	72.1	72.1
Valid	MAN	17	27.9	27.9	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

The table shows that, out of 61 cases surveyed, 44 processes, which correspond to 72.1%, consider that they are female; while 17 cases, corresponding to 27.9%, consider that they are male.

Frequency table Anxiety

Gender Of Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
	MAN	44	72.1	72.1	72.1
Valid	WOMAN	17	27.9	27.9	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

The table shows that, out of a total of 61 cases surveyed, 44 processes, corresponding to 72.1%, are considered female, while 17 cases, corresponding to 27.9%, are considered male.

Correlation levels

Correlations

		Anxiety Assessment Score	Depression Test Score
evaluation score	Correlation coefficient	1,000	,135
	Sig. (bilateral)	.	,299
	N	61	61
Spearman's Rho	Correlation coefficient	,135	1,000
	Sig. (bilateral)	,299	.
	N	61	61

The correlation of anxiety and depression p_v is greater than the significance level; the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

4. Discussion And Conclusions

The high prevalence of anxiety disorders and depression has also been studied in other educational settings for several years (Nogueira Martín et al., 2004; Miller, Surtees, 1991; Guthrie, Black, Shaw, Hamilton, Creed & Tomerson, 1995).

Depression is a mental illness characterized by sadness and loneliness that invades the person. This usually occurs in adolescents with various manifestations concerning their evolutionary conditions, such as irritability, opposition, etc. (Beck & Alford, 2009, p. 08; Moreso & Sans, 2018, p. 28).

However, it is noteworthy that in the study we are referring to in this comparison, the association between sex and the probability of suffering from diseases, in general, is significant, with men being at greater risk.

For anxiety levels according to sex, it is evident in the results that the male sex obtains the highest frequency with 72.1%, at a mild level, as opposed to the female sex with 27.9%, also at a mild level. On the contrary, researchers such as Ardían (2013) and Montoya & Suarez (2014) differ with these results since the male population presents the highest frequencies of anxiety with 53% and 73%, respectively.

Similarly, when considering the levels of depression according to sex, it could be affirmed that once again it is the female sex who presents the highest frequency of symptoms with 72.1% of the population, at a mild level, unlike the male sex, where only 27.9% presented symptoms of mild depression. This coincides with the research of, Vives, González, Sánchez, Fernández & Villanueva (2014), because it was also women who presented more cases of depression with 71%; and with the work of Mena, Cerdán, Pérez & Manrique (2010) where depressive symptomatology was higher in the female sex. However, despite this, discrepancies are found in the research of Mesa, Vázquez & Álvarez (2013) since the males presented a higher frequency of depression.

At the end of the investigation, the following conclusions were reached:

- The present study determined the levels of anxiety and depression in the teaching staff of Regular Basic Education of the Local Educational Management Unit 01, District of

San Juan de Miraflores (Lima-Peru), since there were high percentages of both psychiatric disorders.

- Depression was identified according to gender. The highest percentage in women was 72.1% with mild depression, and in men, it was 27.9% with mild depression.
- Anxiety was identified according to gender. The highest percentage in the male gender with mild anxiety was 72.1%, while in the female gender with mild anxiety was 27.9% cases.

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